

SHORT NOTES

Alcoholysis Reactions of Alkyl Selenates

R. C. Mehrotra and S. N. Mathur

Alkyl selenates were prepared by Meyer and Wagner¹ by the reaction :

(where R is Me, Et, and *n*-Pr). An atmosphere of carbon dioxide was found necessary for the above reaction. Methyl selenate was also obtained by the action of diazomethane on selenic acid².

Alkyl selenites³ have been prepared by the azeotropic dehydration technique, using the reaction of alcohol with selenous acid in presence of benzene. A similar reaction with selenic acid, however, appeared to be unsuccessful due to reduction of hexavalent selenium. In view of the above, the preparation of higher alkyl selenates was attempted by alcoholysis reactions. It has been found that on treating ethyl selenate even with an excess of propanols (*n*- and *iso*), butanols (*n*-, *iso*, *sec*- and *tert*-) and amyl (*iso*, and *tert*-) alcohols in presence of benzene, only one ethoxy group is replaced, yielding mixed esters:

which could be distilled in all cases. The mixed esters have been found to be monomeric in refluxing benzene.

These results are interesting in view of the fact that ethyl selenite³ has been found to interchange both the OEt groups with higher primary alcohols, but only one OEt group with secondary and tertiary alcohols. The steric effect therefore appears to be very high in the case of selenates.

Procedure.—The techniques and the method of drying were the same as described earlier³. Ethyl selenate was prepared by the method of Meyer and Wagner¹. Carbon dioxide was prepared by the action of HCl (dilute) on marble chips and was dried by passing through a battery of bubblers containing H₂SO₄(conc.). Molecular weights were determined in refluxing benzene, using a semimicro ebullimeter with thermistor sensing. Refractive indices were measured by an Abbe refractrometer.

1. *Ber.*, 1922, 53, 1216.

2. Sidgwick, "The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Vol. II. Oxford University Press, 1952.

3. Mehrotra and Mathur, *this Journal*, 1964, 41, 111.

4. Bradley *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3450.

TABLE I

S. No.	Reactants.	Products.	Yield		%Se.	Alcohol (g) in azeotrope		Mol. Wt.	Refractive index.	Refused for.	
			Undistilled.	Distilled.		Found.	Reqd.				Found.
1.	E. S. (2.0 g.) + n-PrOH	O ₂ Se (OEt) (n-OPr) 87°/3mm	3.10g (100%)	2.4-2.0 g. (83.33%)	36.1	36.70	..	207.50	215.12	1.4452	8hr.
2.	E. S. (3.5 g.) + i-PrOH	O ₂ Se (OEt) (i-OPr) 66°/3mm	3.58 g. (95.83%)	2.8-1.65 g. (59%)	36.88	36.70	..	215.50	215.12	1.4552	15
3.	E. S. (3.5 g.) + sec.-BuOH	O ₂ Se (OEt) (sec-OBu) 90°/3.5mm	3.63 g. (84.26%)	2.54-1.4 g. (55.12%)	34.48	34.45	..	258.00	229.15	1.4510	12
4.	E. S. (3.1 g.) + t-BuOH	O ₂ Se (OEt) (t-OBu) 92°/6 mm Very much hydrolysable; decomposes on keeping.	3.25 g. (90%)	2.8-2.1 g. (75%)	34.40	34.45	0.69	268.50	229.15	1.6651	18
5.	E. S. (1.9 g.) + i-Bu OH	O ₂ Se (OEt) (t-OBu) 90°/2.5mm	2.10g. (100%)	2.1-1.75 g. (81%)	34.57	34.45	..	240.40	229.15	1.4530	8
6.	E. S. (2.75 g.) + i-Pentanol	O ₂ Se (OEt) (t-OAm) 87°/6mm	3.25 g. (99.5%)	3.05-2.8 g. (86.36%)	32.56	32.46	..	255.00	243.17	1.4540	8
7.	E. S. (3.7 g.) + i-Pentanol	O ₂ Se (OEt) (t-OAm) 85°/1mm Very much hydrolysable; decomposes on keeping.	2.85 g. (63.7%)	1.8-0.6 g. (59%)	32.48	32.48	0.59	255.70	243.17	1.4540	12

N. B.—E. S. denotes ethyl selenate

*All the alcohols were taken in excess.

**All the products are amber-coloured liquids excepting No. 5, which is a yellow liquid.

Selenium was estimated in the elementary form, using SO_2 in HCl as the precipitating agent. The ethanol in the azeotrope was estimated by an oxidimetric method⁴.

Reaction of Ethyl Selenate with n-Butanol.—To ethyl selenate (2.2 g.) was added an excess of *n*-butanol, followed by benzene, in CO_2 -atmosphere. The reaction was endothermic. The contents were refluxed for 8 hr. under a column and the bubbling of CO_2 was continued. The binary azeotrope of ethanol and benzene, distilling at 68° , was slowly collected. Refluxing was continued till the distilling liquid did not show any tendency of lowering the temperature below 80° . Excess of the solvent was distilled at the column at a high reflux ratio. On removing the volatile contents under reduced pressure, an amber-coloured liquid (2.4 g., 98%) distilling at $90^\circ/1$ mm was obtained; yield 2.4 g to 1.6 g. (66.7%); n_D , 1.4570. [Found: Se, 34.32; M.W., 234.0. $\text{O}_2\text{Se}(\text{OBu}^n)(\text{OEt})$ requires Se, 34.45%; M.W., 229.15].

Similar reactions were carried out in the case of other alcohols (Table I).

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